

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15651306

Dividend Policy Optimality and Performance of Nigerian Listed Oil and Gas Firms

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ABSTRACT

Dividend policy remains one of the most fundamental financial decision policies that a firm makes since it influences firm's overall corporate performance. However, oil and gas firms face unique challenges in balancing dividend distributions with reinvestment needs for growth and sustainability. Hence, this paper seeks to investigate the effect of dividend policy optimality on performance of Nigerian listed oil and gas firms from 2014 to 2023. The study decomposed into dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend stability ratio (DSR), dividend yield (DIY), and dividend retention ratio (DRR) while firm performance was measured using return on equity. Data were sourced from the annual financial reports of seven (7) sampled oil and gas firms from 2014 to 2023. The robust regression analysis served as the main estimation technique. The study confirmed that dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend yield (DIY), and dividend retention ratio (DRR) have positive significant effect on firm performance. However, dividend stability ratio (DSR) has negative insignificant effect on firm performance. Hence, the study concludes that dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend yield (DIY), and dividend retention ratio (DRR) contributes meaningfully to higher firm performance. As such, Nigerian listed oil and gas firms should strive to maintain a balanced dividend policy that combines moderate dividend payouts with adequate earnings retention. Furthermore, oil and gas firms should adopt strategic retention policies that channel retained earnings into productive investments such as asset expansion, technology upgrades, and upstream diversification, which are crucial in the capital-intensive oil and gas sector

Keywords: Dividend Policy Optimality, dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend yield (DIY), and dividend retention ratio (DRR), Performance

INTRODUCTION

Dividend policy remains one of the most fundamental financial decision policy that a firm make since it influences firm's overall corporate performance. In highly capital-intensive sectors such as oil and gas, determining the optimal dividend policy is paramount due to the high volatility of earnings, exposure to global market dynamics, and long-term investment horizons. Since the discovery of oil, the Nigerian oil and gas sector has remained a major contributor to national revenue, economic activity, and economic development. However, oil and gas firms face unique challenges in balancing dividend distributions with reinvestment needs for growth and sustainability (Kumar & Sujit (2022)

The concept of dividend policy optimality seeks to identify the trade-off point where dividend decisions comprising the dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend stability ratio (DSR), dividend yield (DIY), and

dividend retention ratio (DRR) maximize shareholder wealth without compromising the firm's operational efficiency and future profitability. Each of these measures plays a distinct role in shaping investor perceptions and firm valuation. While DPR reflects the portion of earnings distributed to shareholders, DRR indicates the proportion retained for reinvestment. Similarly, DIY serves as an indicator of return on investment, and DSR measures the consistency of dividend payments over time, which can influence investor trust and market confidence (Enakirerhi & Ighosewe, 2024)

Empirical studies from both advanced and emerging countries continue to yield mixed findings. For instance, Njoku and Lee (2024) and Haryono *et al.* (2024) found that dividend payments positively influenced firm performance in Korea—measured through Tobin's Q and market-to-book ratios—but with divergent outcomes across ownership structures. While Chaebol firms benefited from dividend policy (DIP) adjustments, non-Chaebol firms experienced adverse impacts, possibly due to agency conflicts and managerial entrenchment. This raises a critical question about contextual factors that influence the effectiveness of dividend policies.

In the Nigerian context, studies by Lazbery (2024) and Olaoye and Olaniyan (2022) focused on consumer goods firms and reported that dividend yield and stability tend to improve firm performance, while higher payout ratios may dampen it. Meanwhile, Adeiza, Sabo, and Abiola (2020) observed that dividend payout ratios had inconsistent effects on accounting-based performance indicators, suggesting that dividend effects may vary over time and across firm types. These findings highlight the contextual sensitivity of dividend-performance linkages. However, despite the importance of the oil and gas sector to Nigeria's economy, there remains a significant gap in empirical literature specifically investigating the optimal mix of dividend policy components—such as dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend yield (DIY), dividend stability ratio (DSR), and dividend retention ratio (DRR)—and their collective effect on firm performance. This sector, which is capital-intensive and highly exposed to global shocks, requires an evidence-based understanding of how dividend policy decisions can balance shareholder expectations with long-term investment needs.

Furthermore, while studies in Pakistan, Vietnam, Malaysia, and Jordan (e.g., Jatoi & Rasheed, 2023; Nguyen *et al.*, 2021; Foong & Malek, 2022; Kanakriyah, 2020) provide useful insights, their findings cannot be directly applied to Nigeria due to differences in institutional quality, corporate governance structures, investor behavior, and regulatory environments. Given the strategic relevance of dividend decisions in the post-pandemic economic recovery and investor confidence restoration, understanding the optimality of dividend policy in Nigerian listed oil and gas firms becomes imperative. This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by investigating how an optimal combination of DPR, DSR, DIY, and DRR influences firm performance in the Nigerian oil and gas sector, providing insights that can guide policy formulation and strategic corporate financial management.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Kumar and Sujit (2022) emphasize that Dividend policy decision is a strategic decision balancing current shareholder returns and reinvesting for future growth and sustainability. This decision involves assessing whether retained earnings will create more value for shareholders through reinvestment in growth opportunities or whether they should cover dividends/share repurchases. Dividend policy decision, therefore, represents a critical balance between shareholder returns & long-term corporate growth, aiming to maximize value for stakeholders, including shareholders, management, and lenders especially during economic challenges like the Covid 19 (Anastasia Blessing, & Oghenetega, 2021)

One major inference that may be drawn from the above is that both perspectives (dividend payout and dividend retention) emphasize the critical challenge of determining whether earnings will generate more value for shareholders through reinvestment in opportunities or whether they should be distributed as cash dividends or share repurchases. This decision hinges on assessing the company's capacity to leverage earnings for future investments versus meeting shareholder expectations for immediate returns (Ighosewe, Enakirerhi, Agbogun, Atube, & Obaro, 2024). DIP represents a strategic balance between current

shareholder distributions and reinvesting for sustainable growth, aiming to maximize value for all stakeholders, including shareholders, management, and lenders (Onuorah, & Osuji, 2014). The decision on dividend distribution is influenced by several critical factors. First, legal frameworks shaping a company's DIP. Various regulations, such as net profit rules, insolvency rules, and tax regulations, impose essential constraints that guide firms in their dividend decisions (Kumar & Sujit, 2022). Specifically, firms in their growth phases often prioritize retaining earnings for expansion purposes. Retaining profits for reinvestment helps reduce reliance on loans, which incur interest expenses & increase financial risk (Chazi et al., 2022). This strategy supports long-term, sustainable growth but may cause frustration among shareholders that likes dividend now. As these firms focus on expansion & increasing their market presence, shareholders who prioritize short-term income may be disappointed by the reduced DPR. The implication is that firms pursuing growth must manage shareholder expectations carefully and effectively communicate value creation, especially when dividends are reduced or deferred. Meanwhile, market conditions and owner preferences also significantly influence DIP. Firms focusing on long-term growth typically adopt lower DPRs, choosing instead to reinvest earnings into their business. This is often will be highly beneficial to shareholders than immediate DIP (Chazi et al., 2022). However, this approach may not current income over future gains. Additionally, market conditions like economic downturns or volatility, can influence a company's decision to reduce or defer dividends in favor of strengthening its financial position. The implication of these factors is that companies need to align their DIP with both market conditions & shareholder expectations, ensuring that long-term strategies are communicated clearly to mitigate dissatisfaction among shareholders focused on immediate returns. By considering these determinants, companies can craft DIP that align with shareholder expectations while ensuring adequate resources for sustainable growth and stability.

Figure 2.1: Dividend Policy Decision & performance
Source: Author's Computation (2025)

Theoretical Review

The M&M Theory was used to underpin the study. This theory was introduced in 1958. The theory challenges the traditional views on capitalization by positing that in an ideal world (with no taxes, transaction costs, or information asymmetry), a firm's capitalization is irrelevant to its overall capital costs and firm value. This is known as the capitalization irrelevance principle. According to M&M, firm value is factored solely by its assets & operating performance, not by how it finances these assets (whether through debt or equity).

While M&M's model assumes perfect capital markets which rarely exist in reality—it provides a critical benchmark for understanding how factors like taxes, bankruptcy costs, and information asymmetry distort the financing choices firms make. The theory's relevance lies in highlighting the inefficiencies that arise when these ideal conditions do not hold. For instance, tax shields & financial distress costs are often significant in real markets, affecting the capital costs and influencing a firm's investment and DIP.

The M&M theory has important implications for dividend policy decision by emphasizes that if capitalization were irrelevant, firms would not need to adjust dividends based on their mix of borrowings & equity financing. However, in reality, firms with high borrowings might prefer to retain earnings and minimize dividend payout ratio to ensure they have enough liquidity to meet debt obligations.

Empirical Review

Njoku and Lee (2024) examined the link between dividend policies, performance, and market value in the Korean market, considering the distinct structure of Chaebol ownership. Their empirical analysis, which drew on data from 5478 observations of Korean Stock Index, used robust regression model. That is, cash dividends positively influence Tobin's Q and market-to-book ratios, indicating a strong correlation with market value. However, Chaebol & non-Chaebol firms, the impacts were different. For Chaebol firms, the DIP had a positive effect on performance. In contrast, non-Chaebol firms exhibited negative impacts, aligning more with the entrenchment theory, which raises questions about their market value.

Similarly, Haryono, Worokinasih, and Darmawan (2024) investigated the same topic within the context of Korean market firms. Their study also used 5478 observations, focusing on 498 non-financial companies between 2010 & 2021. Consequently, dividend payments had a positive improve performance as indicated by Tobin's Q & market-to-book ratios. However, different patterns were observed when comparing Chaebol & non-Chaebol firms, with the former benefiting from DIP adjustments while the latter suffered due to entrenchment. The research advocates for greater transparency in DIP to improve governance and investor decision-making.

Lazbery (2024) examined the linkages between DIP & performance among Nigerian consumer goods firms. Using secondary data from 21 listed firms for the period 2015-2019, the study used multiple regression techniques to assess the impact of variables like DIY, payout ratio, stability, and ROE. Consequently, DIY impact on ROE significantly, while the DPR reduced it. Overall, dividend stability positively influences ROE.

Jatoi and Rasheed (2023) focused on the impact of DIP on non-financial firms in Pakistan. Their study, from 2010 to 2021, highlighted a DIP (such as DPS, EPS, and DPR) & performance indicators like ROE and ROA. Also, dividend-related variables generally improved performance.

Olaoye and Olaniyan (2022) examined the DIP & performance of consumer goods firms in Nigeria nexus from seven firms from 2014 to 2023 using the Multivariate analysis and found that earnings per share, DPS, and firm size significantly influenced performance.

Nguyen, Pham, and Doan (2021) analyzed the impact of DIP on performance in Vietnamese firms, focusing on 450 Vietnam firms from 2008 to 2019. Their findings suggested that while dividend decisions negatively impacted accounting-based performance (ROA, ROE), they improved market expectations. Specifically, dividend rates positively affected accounting performance but harmed market expectations.

Adeiza, Sabo, and Abiola (2020) explored how DPRs impacted earnings indicators (net profit margin, ROA, and ROE) in Nigeria. The study found that the DPR had mixed effects on earnings, with significant impacts observed in certain years. The study concluded that DIP are paramount in signaling financial capacity & managers adopt policies that enhance value of the firm.

Kanakriyah (2020) studied the linkages between DIP & performance in emerging markets, focusing on 92 firms listed ASE from 2015 to 2019. The research revealed that DIY and payout ratios positively influenced performance, whereas leverage ratios negatively affected ROA.

Ali (2022) analyzed how DIP affected performance in both high- and low-debt environments in Pakistan from 122 non-financial companies from 2006 to 2011, the study found that DPRs were positively linked with performance, particularly in low-leverage firms.

Foong and Malek (2022) investigated the linkages between DIP & performance in publicly listed Malaysian firms, specifically within the consumer products & services sector. The study used ROE and ROA as performance measures and found a DPRs & performance are linear.

Bello and Lasisi (2020) examined the factors influencing DIP in Nigerian firms between 2015 and 2019, showed that DIP were positively linked with business risk and firm lifecycle but negatively affected by tangibility.

3. METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted the *ex-post* facto design given the fact that the data analyzed are secondary in nature, verifiable, reliable and cannot be manipulated by the researchers. Our domain is the oil and gas sector with focus on the nine (9) listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria as at 31st December, 2024. However, seven (7) of the firms were sampled due to data availability. The sampled firms with their identity are presented in Table 1:

Table 3.1: Sampled Firms and their Identities

Company	Firm Identities (ID)
MRS	1
Japaul Gold & Ventures	2
Oando	3
Conoil	4
Capital Oil	5
Eterna	6
Seplat Energy	7

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2025)

Data were sourced primarily from 2014 to 2023. Variables sourced are DPR, DSR, DIY, DRR. These data were gotten from the annual financial reports of the 7 sampled firms between the periods of 2014 and 2023. The Robust Least Square (RLS) Estimation was considered appropriate model for the analysis due to its flexibility, robustness, flexibility, and superior statistical properties compared to conventional OLS estimation technique. Preliminary tests conducted are descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, normality tests, multicollinearity and **Heteroskedasticity test**. The explicit form of the model is presented in Equation 1:

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$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1DPR + \beta_2DSR + \beta_3DIY + \beta_4DRR + \beta_5FSZ + Ut \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where:

- β_0 = Constant
- $\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Coefficient
- Ut = Error Term

Table 2 details the dividend policy and firm performance measures were quantified:

Table 2: Variable Operationalization

Variable	Sign	Nature of Variable	Measurement	Expected Signs
Model 3: DIP & performance				
Dividend Payout Ratio	DPR	Regressor	DPS/EPS	Positive
Dividend Stability Ratio	DSR	Regressor	Dividend Paid/Net Income	Negative
Dividend Yield	DIY	Regressor	Annual Dividend per Share/Share Price *100	Negative
Dividend Retention Ratio	DRR	Regressor	1–Dividend Payout Ratio or Retained Earnings/Net Income	Positive
Firm Size	FSZ	Control	Log of Total Asset	Positive

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2024)

Preliminary Test

Table 3: Summary Statistics

	Mean	Max	Min	Std. Dev.	Observations
ROE	2.967857	46.07000	-56.9	14.67388	70
DPR	1.799429	42.68000	0.000000	5.982058	70
DSR	0.545000	8.050000	0.000000	1.234466	70
DIY	14.36443	71.33000	0.000000	18.56553	70
DRR	0.615000	100.0000	-41.68	13.45225	70
FSZ	7.594707	9.427500	5.647400	0.860818	70

Source: E-Views (2025)

Table 3 focusing on key indicators of profitability and dividend policy variable. ROE has a mean value of 2.97%, with a max. of 46.07% and a min. of -56.9%. This suggests that, though some firms achieve strong shareholder returns, others experience significant financial losses. The high deviation of 14.67% highlights substantial variability in profitability across firms, which may be influenced by differences in dividend policies, reinvestment strategies, & market conditions.

The DPR, has a mean of 1.80%, with a wide range from 0 to 42.68%. The high deviation of 5.98 suggests high margin in firms' approaches to dividend distribution, where some firms reinvest most of their earnings for growth while others prioritize shareholder returns. The variability in DPR may reflect differences in earnings stability, industry practices, and corporate governance policies.

The DSR reported average value of 0.55, with values ranging from 0 to 8.05. This indicates that while some firms maintain steady dividend policies, others have highly fluctuating payouts. The deviation of 1.23 highlights considerable variations in dividend stability, suggesting that some firms face earnings volatility that affects their ability to provide regular dividends.

Dividend yield (DIY) has a mean of 14.36%, with a max. of 71.33% and a min. of 0%. The high deviation of 18.57 indicates that some firms offer substantial dividend returns, while others do not distribute dividends at all. This variability suggests that dividend policies differ significantly across firms, depending on profitability, growth objectives, and investor expectations.

The DRR, which measures the proportion of earnings retained, has a mean value of 0.62. However, its range from -41.68% to 100% highlights substantial differences in firms' reinvestment strategies. Negative values suggest that some firms distribute more dividends than their net income, possibly through earnings retained or external financing. The high deviation of 13.45 further emphasizes disparities in firms' approaches to balancing shareholder returns with reinvestment needs.

Firm size (FSZ), with a mean of 7.59 and a relatively low deviation value of 0.86, indicates that the firms operate within a comparable scale. Big firms may have more stable earnings and established dividend policies, while smaller firms may experience greater variability in profitability and dividend distributions.

Table 4.: Normality Test

	Jarque-Bera	Probability	Observations
ROE	56.66874	0.000000	70
DPR	3467.862	0.000000	70
DSR	1542.456	0.000000	70
DIY	25.38843	0.000003	70
DRR	5579.333	0.000000	70
FSZ	1.138033	0.566082	70

Source: E-Views (2025)

Table 4 reported that ROE, DPR, DSR, DIY, and DRR all having prob. values of 0.000000, rejecting the H0 of normality. Only FSZ is normally distributed. The high Jarque-Bera values for DPR (3467.862) and DRR (5579.333) indicate severe deviations from normality, implying that dividend policy variables are highly skewed or have extreme kurtosis (Ehiedu, Onuorah, & Mbagwu, 2022; Onuorah, 2018).

Table 5: Spearman Correlation

Correlation Cases	ROE	DPR	DSR	DIY	DRR	FSZ
ROE	1.000000					
DPR	-0.147469	1.000000				
DSR	0.306405	0.134069	1.000000			
DIY	0.127909	0.162732	0.114259	1.000000		
DRR	0.145383	-0.099860	-0.134499	-0.162793	1.000000	
FSZ	-0.023812	0.109943	-0.152842	0.161103	-0.109644	1.000000

Source: E-Views (2025)

From Table 5, ROE exhibits a weak inverse association with the DPR at -0.147, indicating that higher DPR tend to have slightly lower ROE. By implication, firms distributing a larger proportion of their earnings as dividends may have fewer internal funds available for reinvestment, potentially limiting their ability to generate higher returns. The inverse association aligning the trade-off theory, where firms must trade off dividend payout and reinvestment strategies to optimize ROE.

The dividend stability ratio (DSR) has a moderate positive correlation with ROE (0.306), implying that firms with more stable dividend policies tend to achieve higher ROE. A stable dividend policy may signal strong soundness and earnings predictability, which can enhance investor confidence and firm valuation. The positive correlation suggests that firms maintaining consistent dividend payments are more likely to generate sustainable returns for shareholders.

Dividend yield (DIY) exhibits a weak positive correlation with ROE (0.128), indicating that firms offering higher dividend yields tend to achieve slightly better profitability. This suggests that firms with attractive dividend yields may attract investors seeking income-generating stocks, potentially driving stock performance and overall firm profitability. However, the weak correlation indicates that other factors, such as earnings growth & market conditions, play a more significant role in determining ROE.

The DRR has a weak positive correlation with ROE (0.145), suggesting that firms retaining a higher proportion of their earnings may experience slightly better ROE. Earnings retained provide a source of internal financing, enabling firms to fund expansion and investment opportunities with less emphasis on

external capital. The positive relationship supports the argument that firms with effective reinvestment strategies can enhance shareholder returns over time.

FSZ shows a negligible inverse association with ROE (-0.024), indicating that firm size has little direct influence on ROE. Big firms gain from large scale and market dominance, but their profitability depends on various operational and financial factors. The low correlation suggests that DIPs impact performance independently of firm size.

Table 6: Multi-collinearity Test

Variables	VIF	TOV	Conclusion
DPR	1.4838	0.6739	No Multi-collinearity Problem Found
DSR	1.2627	0.7920	No Multi-collinearity Problem Found
DIY	1.1266	0.8876	No Multi-collinearity Problem Found
DRR	1.2442	0.8037	No Multi-collinearity Problem Found
FSZ	1.1172	0.8951	No Multi-collinearity Problem Found
Average	1.2469	0.8105	No Multi-collinearity Problem Found

Source: E-Views (2025)

For Table 6 above, the VIF values for all regressors (DPR, DSR, DIY, DRR, and FSZ) range between 1.1172 and 1.4838, with an average of 1.2469. These values are well below the threshold of concern, indicating that the variables do not exhibit significant multicollinearity. Similarly, the TOV values range from 0.6739 to 0.8951, all above the 0.1 threshold. This confirmed that the predictors maintain a reasonable level of independence and that the model did not exhibit any form of multicollinearity (Ebiringa, Onuorah, & Obi, 2014)

Table 7: Heteroskedasticity Test

Three	F-statistic	1.103870	Prob. F(5,64)	0.3672	Homoskedastic
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Source: E-Views (2025)

Table 7 reported an F-statistic value of 1.103870, with a Prob. F value of 0.3672 implying that the variance of the residuals remains constant. Hence, a robust regression was adopted to further endure that our regression estimate are valid for policy formulation.

Table 4.20: DIP & performance-Model Three

Dependent Variable: ROE

Method: Robust Least Squares

Date: 03/08/25 Time: 05:12

Sample: 2014 2023

Included observations: 70

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.463690	10.887780	4.083817	0.0000
DPR	0.282400	2.138062	2.423877	0.0182
DSR	-0.041026	1.033599	-0.396926	0.6914
DIY	0.437201	10.646280	4.106605	0.0000
DRR	0.294392	16.056420	2.593599	0.0118
FSZ	0.359691	1.449809	-3.765800	0.0002

Robust Statistics

R2	0.075949	Adj. R2	0.003757
Rw-squared	0.248020	Adjust Rw-squared	0.248020
Rn-squared statistic	15.60008	Prob(Rn-squared) stat.)	0.008084

Wald Test:

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	4.491554	(4, 64)	0.0029

The *R*-squared value of 0.2480, compared to the conventional *R*-squared of 0.0759, suggests a better model fit under robust conditions. This implies that the regressors explain a higher proportion of the variation in ROE when robust estimation is applied. Furthermore, *r* Heteroskedasticity ensures that model is not significantly overstated due to incorrect standard error estimation.

The Wald test further supports the model's validity by confirming the joint significance. The F-statistic of 4.4916 (prob. value = 0.0029) and Chi-square statistic of 17.9662 (prob. value = 0.0013) indicate strong evidence against the *H*₀. By extension, the regressors have significant effect on ROE, reinforcing the robustness of the model's findings. Overall, Wald test reaffirmed that our model is reliable.

Furthermore, the study confirmed that DPR has a positive significant effect on ROE, with a coeff. of 0.282 and a prob. value of 0.0182. That is, higher DPR tend to experience improved financial performance, supporting the signaling theory of dividends. According to this theory, higher dividend payments signal strong earnings potential and financial stability, boosting investor confidence & firm valuation. The implication is that firms should maintain a consistent & transparent dividend policy to attract investors and enhance market value. On the other hand, DSR exhibits a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with ROE, sustain its DPR over time does not necessarily translate into improved profitability. One possible explanation is that firms prioritizing dividend sustainability may limit reinvestment in growth opportunities, thereby constraining long-term performance. This result implies that while maintaining a stable dividend policy is essential for investor confidence.

The DIY is found to have a positive significant effect on ROE, with a coeff. of 0.437 and a prob. value of 0.0000. This result aligns with investor preference theory, which suggests that investors favor firms with higher DIY as they provide a stable return on investment. A high DIY can make a firm's stock more attractive, potentially leading to an increase in share price and overall firm value. The finding implies that firms should consider dividend yield as an essential factor in their dividend policy to enhance investor appeal and market competitiveness.

Similarly, the DRR exhibits a positive significant effect on ROE, with a coefficient of 0.294 and a prob. value of 0.0118. Earnings retained allow firms to reinvest in expansion opportunities, reducing reliance on debt and mitigating financial risk. The implication is that firms should manage their earnings retained effectively to fund growth initiatives while maintaining an optimal dividend payout structure.

FSZ, however, has a negative significant effect on ROE, with a coeff. of -0.360 and a prob. value of 0.0002. This finding suggests that firms with large asset base; their ROE may decline due to higher operational costs, bureaucratic inefficiencies, & managerial complexities. The result contrasts with economies of scale paradigm, which posits that large-scale firms benefit from cost advantages. Instead, it suggests that firms should focus on operational efficiency and strategic resource allocation rather than merely expanding in size to enhance profitability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study affirms that DIP impact performance, with higher DIP and yields signaling strong soundness, attracting investors and also improving firm performance. The study underscores that dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend yield (DIY), and dividend retention ratio (DRR) have positive significant effect on firm performance. However, dividend stability ratio (DSR) has negative insignificant effect on firm performance. Hence, the study concludes that dividend payout ratio (DPR), dividend yield (DIY), and dividend retention ratio (DRR) contributes meaningfully to higher firm performance. Consequently, the following policy recommendations were made:

1. Nigerian listed oil and gas firms should strive to maintain a **balanced dividend policy** that combines moderate dividend payouts with adequate earnings retention.
2. Since dividend yield has been shown to significantly enhance firm performance, management should consider optimizing dividend yield levels to attract and retain value-driven investors.
3. Firms should adopt strategic retention policies that channel retained earnings into productive investments such as asset expansion, technology upgrades, and upstream diversification, which are crucial in the capital-intensive oil and gas sector.
4. To foster investor trust and reduce information asymmetry, firms should ensure clear and consistent communication of their dividend policies.

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